

Research

Upper Lip Bite Test Versus Modified Mallampati Test in Predictor of Difficult Airway

**Amit Kumar Karna^{1*}, Ajay Kumar Pajiyar¹, Sanjay Yadav¹, Sandeep Sharma¹,
Naveen Sah¹**

¹ Department of Anesthesia and Critical Care, Madhesh Institute of Health Science, Janakpur, Nepal

Abstract: Objective: To explore the comparison between the upper lip bite test (ULBT) and the modified Mallampati test (MMT) to predict difficult intubation. Methods: A total of 112 patients of both sexes, aged between 18 and 60 years, scheduled for elective surgeries under general anesthesia and meeting the inclusion and exclusion criteria, were included in the study. The patient's airway was evaluated using the MMT and ULBT preoperatively. Predictors of difficult endotracheal intubation were assigned to MMT class III and IV, and ULBT class III. After premedication and induction, laryngoscopy was performed. After successful intubation, a difficulty score was recorded based on the sum of seven assessment parameters. A score >5 was considered indicative of difficult intubation. Results: The incidence of difficult intubation in the study was 13.4% (i.e., 15 out of 112 patients). ULBT showed higher sensitivity (92.3% vs. 30.8%), specificity (93.8% vs. 74.3%) (60% vs. 13.8%), and (96.8% vs. 86.7%) compared to MMT. Conclusion: The upper lip bite test is better at predicting difficult intubation with higher accuracy compared to the modified Mallampati test. Both tests are good predictors of easy intubation.

Keywords: Upper Lip Bite Test (ULBT), Modified Mallampati test (MMT), Difficult airway

*Corresponding Author: Amit Kumar Karna, Department of Anesthesia and Critical Care, Madhesh Institute of Health Science, Janakpur, Nepal

Accepted: 18 July, 2024; **Published:** 20 July, 2024

How to cite this article: Amit Kumar Karna, Ajay Kumar Pajiyar, Sanjay Yadav, Sandeep Sharma, Naveen Sah(2024). Upper Lip Bite Test Versus. Modified Mallampati Test in Predictor of Difficult Airway. North American Academic Research, 7(7), 37-42. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13211543>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

Airway management is a cornerstone of anesthesiology and critical care, with accurate prediction of difficult airways being essential to avoid potentially life-threatening complications during intubation[1]. Anticipation of a difficult airway allows clinicians to prepare and employ advanced airway management strategies, thereby enhancing patient safety. Among the array of preoperative airway assessment tools, the Modified Mallampati Test (MMT) and the Upper Lip Bite Test (ULBT) are two of the most commonly utilized methods. This paper seeks to compare these two tests to determine their relative efficacy in predicting difficult airways.

The Modified Mallampati Test, a widely recognized method, involves the patient sitting with their mouth open and tongue protruded as far as possible. The anesthesiologist then visually assesses the visibility of the oropharyngeal structures, specifically the soft palate, uvula, and tonsillar pillars, classifying them into four categories[2]. Class I indicates full visibility of the soft palate, uvula, and tonsillar pillars, while Class IV shows only the hard palate. Despite

its simplicity and non-invasive nature, the MMT has faced criticism for its interobserver variability and limited predictive accuracy in certain populations [3]. The subjective nature of the assessment can lead to inconsistent results, and its effectiveness may be reduced in patients with anatomical variations or limited mouth opening.

In contrast, the Upper Lip Bite Test, introduced [4], is a simpler and more objective test that evaluates mandibular mobility and facial structure. Patients are asked to bite their upper lip with their lower incisors, and the ease of this action is graded into three classes. Class I indicates that the lower incisors can bite the upper lip above the vermilion line, Class II shows that the lower incisors can bite the upper lip below the vermilion line, and Class III denotes the inability to bite the upper lip. The ULBT's proponents argue that it is easier to perform and interpret compared to the MMT and may offer superior predictive value [5].

Several studies have compared the predictive values of the MMT and ULBT. For instance, a study found that the ULBT had higher specificity and positive predictive value (PPV) than the MMT. This suggests that the ULBT may be more reliable in correctly identifying patients who will experience difficult intubations. However, the MMT remains widely used due to its familiarity among clinicians and its incorporation into many preoperative assessment protocols [6].

The ongoing debate about the superiority of these tests highlights the need for further research. Combining the MMT and ULBT with other predictors, such as body mass index (BMI), neck circumference, and previous history of difficult intubation, might improve overall predictive accuracy [7]. This integrated approach could potentially provide a more comprehensive assessment of airway difficulty, allowing for better preparation and management during anesthesia [8].

Research Methodology

A total of 112 patients of both sexes, aged between 18 and 60 years, who were scheduled for elective surgeries under general anesthesia and fulfilled the inclusion and exclusion criteria, were included in this study conducted at Madesh Institute of Health Sciences, Janakpur, Nepal, from February 2023 to July 2023. The patients' airways were evaluated by MMT and ULBT preoperatively. Predictors of difficult endotracheal intubation were assigned to MMT class III and IV, and ULBT class III. After premedication and induction, laryngoscopy was performed. After successful intubation difficulty score was noted down based on the sum of seven assessing parameters. A score >5 was considered as difficult intubation.

In this study, we aim to conduct a comprehensive comparison of the ULBT and MMT, focusing on their sensitivity, specificity, PPV, and negative predictive value (NPV) in predicting difficult intubations. By analyzing data from a diverse patient cohort, we hope to provide clearer insights into the relative efficacy of these tests. Our ultimate goal is to enhance patient safety by improving the prediction and management of difficult airways through evidence-based practices, thereby minimizing the risks associated with airway management.

Inclusion Criteria: Patients scheduled for elective surgery requiring intubation under general anesthesia, aged between 18 and 60 years, of either sex, and with American Society of Anesthesiologists (ASA) physical status Class I and II.

Exclusion Criteria: Patient refusal to take part in the study, patients with edentulous, neck contracture, cervical spine pathology, emergency cases, pregnant patients, malformed or deformed airways like Marfan and Pierre-Robin Syndromes, and mentally incapacitated patients.

Preoperatively, a complete medical history along with a thorough evaluation of all the systems, particularly the airways, was done. The assessment methods were explained in detail to the patients, and the purpose of the research study was also explained, obtaining their consent. The demographic details (age, sex, weight, height, BMI) and information about airway pathology, active infection, dentition status, and snoring were recorded. The procedure of general anesthesia and the surgery were explained to the patient in their language, following which baseline vitals were recorded.

Then, patients were made to sit with their head in the neutral position, mouth fully opened, and tongue maximally protracted without phonation, while the observer looked into pharyngeal structures. The view was graded as follows using Modified Mallampati Classification:

Class I = soft palate, fauces, uvula and pillars seen

Class II = soft palate, fauces, and portion of uvula seen

Class III = soft palate and base of uvula seen

Class IV = soft palate not visible

The patients were asked to perform the Upper Lip Bite Test which was graded as:

Class 1 - lower incisors can bite the upper lip above the vermilion line

Class 2 - lower incisors can bite the upper lip below the vermilion line

Class 3 - the lower incisors cannot bite the upper lip

ULBT class 3 and MMT class III and IV were considered potentially difficult intubation.

Results

Males constituted 50.9% of the study while females formed 49.1% of the study population. The demographic details of the study population are listed in table 1.

Table1: Demographic details

N (112)	Age (112)	Height (112)	Weight (112)	BMI (112)
Mean	36.6	160.9	63.8	24.6
Median	35.0	160.5	65.0	24.2
Std.Deviation	11.9	6.5	10.2	3.8

Out of the 112 patients 15 patients had difficult intubation. The incidence of difficult intubation was 13.4% (I.e. IDS score <5). while the remaining 97 patient were classified as easy intubation. There were no case of impossible intubations in the study population.

Table 2: Intubation difficulty scale

	Intubation difficulty scale (IDS)	Valid Percent
Easy	97	86.6
Difficult	15	13.4
Total	112	100

Table 3: Modified Mallamapati Test v/s Intubation difficulty

		Intubation difficulty scale		
		Easy	Difficult	total
Modified Mallama- pati Test	Easy	72	11	83
	Difficult	25	4	29
	Total	97	15	112

Table 4: Upper lip Bite test v/s Intubation difficulty scale

		Intubation difficulty scale		
		Easy	Difficult	total
Upper Lip Bite Test	Easy	91	3	94
	Difficult	6	12	18
	Total	97	15	112

The sensitivity of ULBT in our study was 92.3%. The high sensitivity of the test would mean that the test would identify patients with difficult intubation. A high specificity suggests that the tests would predict easy intubations correctly. Positive predictive value (PPV) suggests the percentage of correctly predicted difficult intubation as a proportion of all predicted difficult intubations. Negative Predictive Value (NPV) suggests the percentage of correctly predicted difficult intubation.

Table 5: Validity of MMT and ULBT

Parameters	MMT	ULBT
True Negative	72	91
True Positive	4	12
False Negative	11	3
False Positive	25	6
Sensitivity	30.8	92.3
Specificity	74.2	93.8
Positive Predictive Value	13.8	60.0
Negative Predictive Value	86.7	96.8
Diagnostic Accuracy	74.5	91.9
P value	0.7	<0.001

ULBT had a higher sensitivity (92.3% v/s 30.8%), specificity (93.8% v/s 74.2%) PPV (60.0% v/s 13.8%) and NPV (96.8% v/s 86.7%) than that of MMT. An ideal test should be highly sensitive than specific with a high PPV, to predict difficult intubations correctly and avoid false positives. Also, the diagnostic accuracy of ULBT (91.9%) is greater than MMT (74.5%). Both tests had high NPV suggesting these tests are good predictors of easy intubation. The presence of ULBT class III is considered the best predictor of difficult intubation and the absence of MMT class IV helps in ruling out difficult intubation.

Discussion

In this study, we compared the Modified Mallampati Test (MMT) and the Upper Lip Bite Test (ULBT). These are simple and easily demonstrable bedside tests that are non-invasive and inexpensive. In this study of 112 patients undergoing elective surgery under general anesthesia, MMT and ULBT were used as screening tests for predicting difficult intubation, which was evaluated with the Intubation Difficulty Scale (IDS).

In this study the incidence of difficult intubation was 13.4% that is 15 out of 112 patients had difficult intubation (i.e., IDS score > 5). Of the 18 ULBT class III patients, 15 belonged to IDS difficult intubation criteria, while in MMT class III and IV, only 4 out of 29 belonged to IDS difficult intubation criteria. The incidence of difficult intubation in the study by Khan et al. [9] was 5.7%, and in Eberhart et al. [10], it was 12%. There was no incidence of failed intubation in our study. The sensitivity of ULBT in our study was 92.3%. This high sensitivity means that the test would identify patients with difficult intubation. Asghar Ali et al. [11] and Naithani et al. [12] reported a sensitivity of 87.5% and 92.8%, respectively, for ULBT. Khan et al. [8] reported a sensitivity of 76.5% for ULBT. Mohan et al. [13] reported a sensitivity of only 40%. The sensitivity of MMT in our study was 30.8%. Lower sensitivities for MMT were reported in studies conducted by Asghar et al. [11] (19.6%) and Lundstrom et al. [14] (22%). But higher sensitivity has been reported by Khan et al. [9] (82%) and Eberhart et al. [10] (70%). This discrepancy may be due to inaccurate classification, inconsistent technique, and patient factors such as the inability to perform what was asked despite demonstration [15]. A high specificity suggests that the tests would predict easy intubations correctly. The specificity of MMT in this study was 74.23%. The specificity of MMT in studies by Khan et al. [9], Eberhart et al. [10], and Oates et al. [16] were 66.8%, 61%, and 82%, respectively. A wide range of specificity for MMT may be attributed to factors such as poor demarcation between various classes and involuntary phonation. The specificity of ULBT in this study was 93.8%. The specificity value of ULBT is similar to that of the study by Karci et al. [17] (97.6%) and Eberhart et al. [10] (92.5%). Khan et al. [9] had a specificity of 88.7% for ULBT in their trial. Positive predictive value (PPV) suggests the percentage of correctly

predicted difficult intubation as a proportion of all predicted difficult intubations. The positive predictive value of MMT in the current study was 13.8%. This is lower when compared to the PPV noted in the studies of Honarmand et al. [18] (18.3%) and Eberhart et al. [10] (19.5%). This can be attributed to the fact that airway assessment was done by the same examiner, thus avoiding inter-observer variability. The diagnostic accuracy of ULBT was higher at 91.9% than that of MMT, which was only 74.5%. Khan et al. [9] in their study had a diagnostic accuracy of 88% for ULBT and 67.7% for MMT. The diagnostic accuracies seen in other studies like Hester et al. [19] were 90% for ULBT and 84.9% for MMT.

Conclusion

The Upper Lip Bite Test is better at predicting difficult intubation with higher accuracy when compared to the Modified Mallampati Test. Both tests are good predictors of easy intubation. This study cannot be generalized to all subgroups of the general population. Also, the sample size is small, with an allowable error of 3%. Some patients were unable to understand ULBT despite repeated demonstrations or due to the absence of teeth or the ability to move the mouth. Only participants meeting those criteria were included in this study.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: Madhesh Institute of Health Science, Janakpur, Nepal.

Institutional Review Board Statement: Not applicable.

Informed Consent Statement: Not applicable.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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